

The Location of the Nontrivial Zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function on the Critical Line

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Abstract

The zeta series $\zeta(s) = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{1}{n^s}$ diverges when the real part of s , denoted σ , is less than or equal to 1. However, its divergence is not without value. In this paper, we found that the partial sum $\zeta_K(s) = \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{1}{n^s}$ is asymptotically equivalent to the sequence $\frac{1}{1-s} K^{1-s}$ where $K \rightarrow \infty$ & $\sigma > 0$. And for a given σ , the two sequences exhibit their fastest order of asymptotic convergence at the nontrivial zeros of the zeta function. We also derive another asymptotic equivalence

$$s(1-s)\zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1-s) \sim K \quad : K \rightarrow \infty \quad \& \quad \sigma > 0$$

And we proved that at the critical line ($\sigma = 1/2$) the equivalence again displays its fastest order of convergence at the nontrivial zeros of $\zeta(s)$. Expanding the above asymptotic relation at $\sigma = 1/2$, we obtain the following identity:

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{4} + t^2 \right) \frac{1}{K} \left\{ \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{\sqrt{n}} \right]^2 + \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{\sqrt{n}} \right]^2 \right\} = 1$$

With the convergence of this limit again being fastest at the nontrivial zeros of $\zeta(s)$. This behavior provides the foundation for a numerical procedure capable of identifying the locations of the nontrivial zeros on the critical line.

Introduction

The Riemann zeta function is initially defined by the series

$$\zeta(s) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}$$

which converges only when the real part of $s = \sigma + it$ satisfies $\sigma > 1$. In the domain $0 < \sigma \leq 1$, the function can be analytically continued using the alternating zeta series, defined as

$$\eta(s) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-1} \frac{1}{n^s}$$

with the relationship

$$\frac{\eta(s)}{1 - 2^{1-s}} \quad : \quad \sigma > 0$$

To extend the definition of $\zeta(s)$ to the entire complex plane (except at $s = 1$, where it has a simple pole), Riemann derived a functional equation [1]. It has been proven that all nontrivial zeros of the zeta function lie within the critical strip $0 < \sigma < 1$ [2], and the famous Riemann Hypothesis asserts that all such nontrivial zeros lie on the critical line $\sigma = \frac{1}{2}$.

The Zeta Series in the Critical Strip

We start by defining the sums of the first $2N$ elements of the zeta and eta series as follows

$$\zeta_{2N}(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{2N} \frac{1}{n^s} \quad , \quad \eta_{2N}(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{2N} (-1)^{n-1} \frac{1}{n^s}$$

Where $s = \sigma + it$ is a complex variable $\neq 1$ and $\sigma > 0$

Jonathan Sondow in 2003 [2], in his quest to find a second proof that $\eta(s_n) = 0 : s_n = 1 + i n \frac{2\pi}{\log 2}$ ($n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$), derived and used the equation below

$$\eta_{2N}(s) = (1 - 2^{1-s})\zeta_{2N}(s) + 2^{1-s}N^{1-s} \left[\frac{1 - 2^{1-s}}{s-1} - d_N(s) \right] \quad (1)$$

Where: $d_N(s) = \frac{1-2^{1-s}}{s-1} - \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \left(1 + \frac{k}{N}\right)^{-s}$ and $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} d_N(s) = 0$

The derivation of equation (1) is shown in appendix A of this paper.

We divide both sides of (1) by $(1 - 2^{1-s})$ and we get

$$\frac{\eta_{2N}(s)}{1 - 2^{1-s}} = \zeta_{2N}(s) - (2N)^{1-s} \left[\frac{1}{1-s} \right] - (2N)^{1-s} \left[\frac{d_N(s)}{1 - 2^{1-s}} \right] \quad (2)$$

Calling $2N = K$ and sending $K \rightarrow \infty$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\eta_K(s)}{1 - 2^{1-s}} &= \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \left[\zeta_K(s) - \frac{K^{1-s}}{1-s} - \frac{1}{1 - 2^{1-s}} K^{1-s} d_K(s) \right] \\ \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\eta_K(s)}{1 - 2^{1-s}} &= \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \left[\zeta_K(s) - \frac{K^{1-s}}{1-s} \right] - \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{1}{1 - 2^{1-s}} K^{1-s} d_K(s) \right] \end{aligned}$$

From the analytic continuation of the zeta function, we recognize that the sum $\frac{\eta_K(s)}{1-2^{1-s}}$ goes to $\zeta(s)$ when K goes to infinity. And in the appendix B of this paper, we prove that

$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} K^{1-s} d_K(s) = 0$ And replacing $\zeta_K(s) = \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{1}{n^s}$, we obtain

$$\zeta(s) = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{1}{n^s} - \frac{K^{1-s}}{1-s} \right]$$

Which is consistent with the expression we get for $\zeta(s)$ from the Euler-Maclaurin formula [3]

Let us now go back to Equation (2), after replacing $2N = K$, we divide both sides by $\frac{K^{1-s}}{1-s}$, and rearranging we obtain

$$\frac{\zeta_K(s)}{\left(\frac{K^{1-s}}{1-s}\right)} = 1 + (1-s) \frac{\left[\frac{\eta_K(s)}{1 - 2^{1-s}} \right]}{K^{1-s}} + \left(\frac{1-s}{1 - 2^{1-s}} \right) d_K(s) \quad : K \in 2\mathbb{N} \quad (3)$$

Sending K to infinity, the sum $\left[\frac{\eta_K(s)}{1-2^{1-s}} \right]$ goes to $\zeta(s)$, and consequently $\frac{\left[\frac{\eta_K(s)}{1-2^{1-s}} \right]}{K^{1-s}}$ goes to zero and we know that $\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d_K(s)}{2} = 0$ and therefore we obtain

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\zeta_K(s)}{\left(\frac{K^{1-s}}{1-s}\right)} = 1 \quad : \quad \sigma > 0 \quad (4)$$

or

$$\zeta_K(s) \sim \frac{1}{1-s} K^{1-s} \quad : \quad K \rightarrow \infty \quad \& \quad \sigma > 0 \quad (5)$$

In Figures 1 & 2 we show the asymptotic convergence between $\zeta_K(s)$ and $\frac{1}{1-s} K^{1-s}$ when $s = 0.7 + i15$, and in Figures 3 & 4 we show that convergence when $s = s_0 = 0.5 + i14.134$ (first nontrivial zero of zeta on the critical line).

Figure1: Real part of zeta and $\frac{1}{1-s} K^{1-s}$ when $s = 0.7 + i15$

Figure2: Imaginary part of zeta and $\frac{1}{1-s} K^{1-s}$ when $s = 0.7 + i15$

Figure3: Real part of zeta and $\frac{1}{1-s} K^{1-s}$ when $s = 0.5 + i14.134$

Figure4: Imaginary part of zeta and $\frac{1}{1-s} K^{1-s}$ when $s = 0.5 + i14.134$

In the following we will demonstrate that for a given σ , the order of asymptotic convergence of Equation (5) is the highest when s is a nontrivial zero of zeta.

Let us assume $s_0 = \sigma_0 + it_0$ is a nontrivial zero of zeta and let us consider another point $\hat{s} = \sigma_0 + it$ where $t \neq t_0$ and let us compare the convergence order of equation (4) at the two points s_0 and \hat{s}

$$r = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\left| \frac{\zeta_K(s_0)}{\left(\frac{K^{1-s_0}}{1-s_0}\right)} - 1 \right|}{\left| \frac{\zeta_K(\hat{s})}{\left(\frac{K^{1-\hat{s}}}{1-\hat{s}}\right)} - 1 \right|}$$

Replacing from Equation (3) we get

$$r = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\left| (1-s_0) \frac{\left[\frac{\eta_K(s_0)}{1-2^{1-s_0}} \right]}{K^{1-s_0}} + \left(\frac{1-s_0}{1-2^{1-s_0}} \right) d_K(s_0) \right|}{\left| (1-s_1) \frac{\left[\frac{\eta_K(\hat{s})}{1-2^{1-\hat{s}}} \right]}{K^{1-\hat{s}}} + \left(\frac{1-\hat{s}}{1-2^{1-\hat{s}}} \right) d_K(\hat{s}) \right|}$$

$$r = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\left| \frac{(1-s_0) \left[\frac{\eta_K(s_0)}{1-2^{1-s_0}} \right] + K^{1-s_0} \left(\frac{1-s_0}{1-2^{1-s_0}} \right) d_K(s_0)}{K^{1-s_0}} \right|}{\left| \frac{(1-s_1) \left[\frac{\eta_K(\hat{s})}{1-2^{1-\hat{s}}} \right] + K^{1-\hat{s}} \left(\frac{1-\hat{s}}{1-2^{1-\hat{s}}} \right) d_K(\hat{s})}{K^{1-\hat{s}}} \right|}$$

$$r = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\left| \frac{(1-s_0) \left[\frac{\eta_K(s_0)}{1-2^{1-s_0}} \right] + K^{1-s_0} \left(\frac{1-s_0}{1-2^{1-s_0}} \right) d_K(s_0)}{K^{1-\sigma_0}} \right|}{\left| \frac{(1-s_1) \left[\frac{\eta_K(\hat{s})}{1-2^{1-\hat{s}}} \right] + K^{1-\hat{s}} \left(\frac{1-\hat{s}}{1-2^{1-\hat{s}}} \right) d_K(\hat{s})}{K^{1-\sigma_0}} \right|}$$

$$r = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\left| (1 - s_0) \left[\frac{\eta_K(s_0)}{1 - 2^{1-s_0}} \right] + K^{1-s_0} \left(\frac{1 - s_0}{1 - 2^{1-s_0}} \right) d_K(s_0) \right|}{\left| (1 - s_1) \left[\frac{\eta_K(\hat{s})}{1 - 2^{1-\hat{s}}} \right] + K^{1-\hat{s}} \left(\frac{1 - \hat{s}}{1 - 2^{1-\hat{s}}} \right) d_K(\hat{s}) \right|}$$

Let us examine the magnitude of the numerator

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| (1 - s_0) \left[\frac{\eta_K(s_0)}{1 - 2^{1-s_0}} \right] + K^{1-s_0} \left(\frac{1 - s_0}{1 - 2^{1-s_0}} \right) d_K(s_0) \right| \\ & \leq \left| (1 - s_0) \left[\frac{\eta_K(s_0)}{1 - 2^{1-s_0}} \right] \right| + \left| K^{1-s_0} \left(\frac{1 - s_0}{1 - 2^{1-s_0}} \right) d_K(s_0) \right| \end{aligned}$$

As stated before, in Appendix B of this paper, we show that $\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} K^{1-s} d_K(s) = 0$. And since s_0 is a zero of zeta $\zeta(s_0) = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\eta_K(s_0)}{1 - 2^{1-s_0}} = 0$ therefore by the squeeze theorem

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \left| (1 - s_0) \left[\frac{\eta_K(s_0)}{1 - 2^{1-s_0}} \right] + K^{1-s_0} \left(\frac{1 - s_0}{1 - 2^{1-s_0}} \right) d_K(s_0) \right| = 0$$

For the denominator of r , we know that \hat{s} is not a zero of zeta and therefore

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\eta_K(\hat{s})}{1 - 2^{1-\hat{s}}} \neq 0 \implies \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \left| (1 - s_1) \left[\frac{\eta_K(\hat{s})}{1 - 2^{1-\hat{s}}} \right] + K^{1-\hat{s}} \left(\frac{1 - \hat{s}}{1 - 2^{1-\hat{s}}} \right) d_K(\hat{s}) \right| \neq 0$$

And consequently $r = 0$

And therefore, for a given σ the Equation 5 has the fastest asymptotic convergence order when s is a nontrivial zero of zeta.

The Location of the Nontrivial Zeros of Zeta on the Critical Line

We rewrite Equation (5) for the argument $(1 - s)$ and it becomes

$$\zeta_K(1 - s) \sim \frac{1}{s} K^\sigma \quad : K \rightarrow \infty \quad \& \quad \sigma > 0 \quad (6)$$

Like Equation (5), for a given $(1 - \sigma)$ Equation 6, exhibits the fastest order of asymptotic convergence when $(1 - s)$ is a nontrivial zero of the zeta function. By the known symmetry of the zeta's function nontrivial zeros, if s is a nontrivial zero, then so is $(1 - s)$. When $\sigma = 1/2$ (i.e., on the critical line), we have $\sigma = 1 - \sigma$ and therefore both Equations (5) and (6) attain their fastest order of asymptotic convergence at the nontrivial zeros of zeta.

Consequently, their product

$$s(1 - s) \zeta_K(s) \zeta_K(1 - s) \sim K \quad : K \rightarrow \infty \quad \& \quad \sigma > 0 \quad (7)$$

when $\sigma = 1/2$, also achieves its fastest order of asymptotic convergence at the nontrivial zeros of zeta.

Let us expand the left-hand side of (6), the constant $s(1 - s)$ can be written as

$$s(1 - s) = (\sigma + it)(1 - \sigma - it) = [\sigma(1 - \sigma) + t^2] + it(1 - 2\sigma)$$

And the product $\zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1 - s)$ is equal to

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1 - s) &= \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{1}{n^s} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{1}{m^{1-s}} \\ \zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1 - s) &= \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{n^\sigma} - i \frac{\sin t \log n}{n^\sigma} \right] \left[\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\cos(-t \log m)}{m^{1-\sigma}} - i \frac{\sin(-t \log m)}{m^{1-\sigma}} \right] \\ \zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1 - s) &= \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{n^\sigma} - i \frac{\sin t \log n}{n^\sigma} \right] \left[\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log m}{m^{1-\sigma}} + i \frac{\sin t \log m}{m^{1-\sigma}} \right]\end{aligned}$$

The imaginary part of the LHS of eq (6) is

$$\begin{aligned}Im[s(1 - s)\zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1 - s)] &= \\ [\sigma(1 - \sigma) + t^2] &\left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{n^\sigma} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log m}{m^{1-\sigma}} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{n^\sigma} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log m}{m^{1-\sigma}} \right] + \\ t(1 - 2\sigma) &\left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{n^\sigma} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log m}{m^{1-\sigma}} + \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{n^\sigma} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log m}{m^{1-\sigma}} \right]\end{aligned}$$

when $\sigma = 1/2$

$$\begin{aligned}Im[s(1 - s)\zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1 - s)]_{\sigma=1/2} &= \\ \left[\frac{1}{2}\left(1 - \frac{1}{2}\right) + t^2\right] &\left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{n^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log m}{m^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{n^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log m}{m^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right] + \\ t\left(1 - 2\frac{1}{2}\right) &\left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{n^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log m}{m^{\frac{1}{2}}} + \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{n^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log m}{m^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right]\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}Im[s(1 - s)\zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1 - s)]_{\sigma=1/2} &= \\ \left[\frac{1}{4} + t^2\right] [0] &+ \\ t(0) \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{n^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log m}{m^{\frac{1}{2}}} + \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{n^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log m}{m^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right] &= 0\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, at the critical line the imaginary part of the left-hand side of equation 7 is zero. How about the real part?

$$\begin{aligned} & \operatorname{Re}[s(1-s)\zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1-s)] = \\ & [\sigma(1-\sigma) + t^2] \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{n^\sigma} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log m}{m^{1-\sigma}} + \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{n^\sigma} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log m}{m^{1-\sigma}} \right] - \\ & t(1-2\sigma) \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{n^\sigma} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log m}{m^{1-\sigma}} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{n^\sigma} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log m}{m^{1-\sigma}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

when $\sigma = 1/2$

$$\begin{aligned} & \operatorname{Re}[s(1-s)\zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1-s)]_{\sigma=1/2} = \\ & \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \right) + t^2 \right] \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{n^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log m}{m^{1-\frac{1}{2}}} + \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{n^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log m}{m^{1-\frac{1}{2}}} \right] \\ & \operatorname{Re}[s(1-s)\zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1-s)]_{\sigma=1/2} = \left(\frac{1}{4} + t^2 \right) \left\{ \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{\sqrt{n}} \right]^2 + \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{\sqrt{n}} \right]^2 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Equation (7) is equivalent to

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{s(1-s)\zeta_K(s)\zeta_K(1-s)}{K} = 1 \quad : \quad \& \quad \sigma > 0$$

And when $\sigma = 1/2$ it becomes

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{4} + t^2 \right) \frac{1}{K} \left\{ \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{\sqrt{n}} \right]^2 + \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{\sqrt{n}} \right]^2 \right\} = 1 \quad (8)$$

We define

$$\Omega_K(t) = \left(\frac{1}{4} + t^2 \right) \frac{1}{K} \left\{ \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\cos t \log n}{\sqrt{n}} \right]^2 + \left[\sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\sin t \log n}{\sqrt{n}} \right]^2 \right\}$$

$\Omega_K(t)$ converges to 1 at the fastest order when $t=t_0$ (at the location of the nontrivial zeros of zeta). We know from the Asymptotic Analysis that if we have two sequences a_k and b_k both converging to L , a_k converges asymptotically faster to L than b_k if

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{a_k - L}{b_k - L} \right| = 0$$

Therefore, t_0 satisfies the following equation

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{\Omega_K(t_0) - 1}{\Omega_K(t_0 + \Delta) - 1} \right| = 0 \quad (9)$$

for any $\Delta <$ the distance between two consecutive t_0

Numerical Procedure to Find the Location of the Nontrivial Zeros of Zeta on the Critical Line

The above equation can be implemented numerically to identify the location of the nontrivial zeros of zeta on the critical line. The numerical procedure goes as follows:

- 1- We calculate $\lambda_k = \left| \frac{\Omega_K(t) - 1}{\Omega_K(t - \delta) - 1} \right|$ and $\lambda_L = \left| \frac{\Omega_L(t) - 1}{\Omega_L(t - \delta) - 1} \right|$
Where K and L are two different large values (e.g., 1,000,000 and 3,000,000) and δ is a small step (e.g., 0.1)
- 2- We move on the critical line with ascending values of t by a step of δ . And for every t we calculate λ_k and λ_L
- 3- When **both** λ_k and λ_L start dropping towards zero we know that we are approaching a t_0 (see figure 5 below)
- 4- At the point when λ_k and λ_L reverse direction and shoot up to a high value, we know that we crossed a t_0
- 5- We retract t by two steps (2δ) to ensure that we stand before a t_0 and we use a smaller step (e.g., we divide δ by 10), and we move forward again with only one λ the one that has the higher iterations number (in this case $\lambda_L = 3,000,000$) as illustrated in figure 6.
- 6- We repeat step 4 & 5 as many times as needed to achieve the desired accuracy.

Figure 5: Both λ_{1m} and λ_{3m} shooting up at the same location identifying the first nontrivial zero of zeta

	t	r
	13.900000001490116	1.3110421479729175
	14.000000002980232	0.25842127095252145
	14.100000004470348	0.61703722918975601
	14.200000005960465	0.61648516379981223
First crossing of the first zero and retraction by 0.2	14.300000007450581	8.2148977382194175
	14.110000004246831	1.0000000000000000
	14.120000004023314	0.53884384906529585
	14.130000003799796	0.27916237980642233
	14.140000003576279	0.93122781851082601
Second crossing of the first zero and retraction by 0.02	14.150000003352761	2.2273376158352831
	14.131000003730878	1.0000000000000000
	14.132000003661960	0.71841175691229135
	14.133000003593043	0.62031690392248878
	14.134000003524125	0.40813423280109888
	14.135000003455207	0.39963375549011579
Third crossing of the first zero and retraction by 0.002	14.136000003386289	4.3733443235862632
	14.134100003514323	1.0000000000000000
	14.134200003504520	0.83474380539908080
	14.134300003494718	0.80273634372842778
	14.134400003484916	0.75514554715842419
	14.134500003475114	0.67692567466744482
	14.134600003465312	0.52447018791126296
	14.134700003455509	9.66327394964611662E-02
Forth crossing of the first zero and retraction by 0.0002	14.134800003445707	8.3140487379359389
	14.134610003464150	1.0000000000000000
	14.134620003462987	0.90054798547043599
	14.134630003461825	0.88960553768115358
	14.134640003460663	0.87595185223788584
	14.134650003459501	0.85843678008938988
	14.134660003458339	0.83515248357926959
	14.134670003457177	0.80268648341658609
	14.134680003456015	0.75427406233112292
	14.134690003454853	0.67434192399222374
	14.134700003453690	0.51725072852513000
	14.134710003452528	6.70457184569483143E-02
First nontrivial zero of zeta function	14.134720003451366	12.910062076601501

Figure 6: Output of the numerical calculation leading to identifying the first nontrivial zero of zeta

It is important to mention that the above procedure can easily predict the nontrivial zeros with the accuracy of the first 4 or 5 decimal points as illustrated above for the first zero. However, for accuracy beyond 5 decimal points the prediction requires significantly large values for K, higher precision algorithm and consequently more computing memory.

References:

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Appendix A: Derivation of Sondow equation for $\eta_{2N}(s)$

We call ζ_{2N} and η_{2N} the sum of the first $2N$ terms of the zeta and eta series as follows

$$\zeta_{2N}(s) = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \dots + \frac{1}{N^s} + \frac{1}{(N+1)^s} + \frac{1}{(N+2)^s} \dots + \frac{1}{(2N)^s}$$

$$\eta_{2N}(s) = 1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{4^s} + \dots + \frac{1}{N^s} - \frac{1}{(N+1)^s} + \frac{1}{(N+2)^s} \dots - \frac{1}{(2N)^s}$$

And if we calculate $\eta_{2N}(s) - \zeta_{2N}(s)$ we find it equal to

$$\eta_{2N}(s) - \zeta_{2N}(s) = -2\frac{1}{2^s} - 2\frac{1}{4^s} - \dots - 2\frac{1}{(2N)^s}$$

Factoring out $\left(-2\frac{1}{2^s}\right)$ yields

$$\eta_{2N}(s) - \zeta_{2N}(s) = -2^{1-s} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \dots + \frac{1}{N^s}\right)$$

What we have in parenthesis is the sum of the first N terms of zeta, therefore

$$\eta_{2N}(s) - \zeta_{2N}(s) = -2^{1-s} \zeta_N(s)$$

And $\zeta_N(s)$ can be written as

$$\zeta_N(s) = \zeta_{2N}(s) - \sum_{n=N+1}^{2N} n^{-s}$$

Replacing $\zeta_N(s)$ we get

$$\eta_{2N}(s) - \zeta_{2N}(s) = -2^{1-s} \left[\zeta_{2N}(s) - \sum_{n=N+1}^{2N} n^{-s} \right]$$

Rearranging gives

$$\eta_{2N}(s) = (1 - 2^{1-s})\zeta_{2N}(s) + 2^{1-s} \left[\sum_{n=N+1}^{2N} n^{-s} \right]$$

$\left[\sum_{n=N+1}^{2N} n^{-s} \right]$ can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=N+1}^{2N} n^{-s} &= \sum_{k=1}^N (N+k)^{-s} = \sum_{k=1}^N \left[N \left(1 + \frac{k}{N} \right) \right]^{-s} = \\ &= N^{-s} \sum_{k=1}^N \left(1 + \frac{k}{N} \right)^{-s} = N^{1-s} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \left(1 + \frac{k}{N} \right)^{-s} \\ &= N^{1-s} \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \left(1 + \frac{k}{N} \right)^{-s} \end{aligned}$$

And replacing $\sum_{n=N+1}^{2N} n^{-s}$ in the last equation gives

$$\eta_{2N}(s) = (1 - 2^{1-s})\zeta_{2N}(s) + 2^{1-s} N^{1-s} \left[\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \left(1 + \frac{k}{N} \right)^{-s} \right]$$

$\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \left(1 + \frac{k}{N} \right)^{-s}$ is the Riemann sum of the integral $\int_0^1 (1+x)^{-s} dx$ (where $x = \frac{k}{N}$). The difference, $d_N(s)$, between the integral $\int_0^1 (1+x)^{-s} dx$ and its Riemann sum goes to 0 when N goes to infinity, and is equal to

$$d_N(s) = \int_0^1 (1+x)^{-s} dx - \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \left(1 + \frac{k}{N} \right)^{-s}$$

When $s \neq 1$

$$\int_0^1 (1+x)^{-s} dx = \left[\frac{(1+x)^{-s+1}}{-s+1} \right]_1^2 = \left[\frac{2^{-s+1}}{-s+1} - \frac{1^{-s+1}}{-s+1} \right] = \frac{1 - 2^{1-s}}{s-1}$$

And $d_N(s)$ becomes equal to

$$d_N(s) = \frac{1 - 2^{1-s}}{s-1} - \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \left(1 + \frac{k}{N}\right)^{-s}$$

Replacing $\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \left(1 + \frac{k}{N}\right)^{-s}$ into the equation of $\eta_{2N}(s)$ we get

$$\eta_{2N}(s) = (1 - 2^{1-s})\zeta_{2N}(s) + 2^{1-s}N^{1-s} \left[\frac{1 - 2^{1-s}}{s-1} - d_N(s) \right]$$

Appendix B: Poof of $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} (2N)^{1-s} \left[\frac{1-2^{1-s}}{s-1} - \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \left(1 + \frac{k}{N}\right)^{-s} \right] = 0$

We call $d_N(s) = \left[\frac{1-2^{1-s}}{s-1} - \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \left(1 + \frac{k}{N}\right)^{-s} \right]$ and as shown in appendix A it is the difference (error) between the definite integral $\int_0^1 (1+x)^{-s} dx$ and its Riemann sum as listed below

$$d_N(s) = \int_0^1 (1+x)^{-s} dx - \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \left(1 + \frac{k}{N}\right)^{-s}$$

The error in each interval (as shown in figure 7) is bounded by $\left| \frac{1}{N} \left[\left(1 + \frac{k+1}{N}\right)^{-s} - \left(1 + \frac{k}{N}\right)^{-s} \right] \right|$ (see figure 8)

Figure 7: The error between $\int_0^1 (1+x)^{-s} dx$ and its Riemann sum

Figure 7: The upper limit of the error between $\int_0^1 (1+x)^{-s} dx$ and its Riemann sum

Using the Mean Value Theorem, there exists a point in the interval where

$$\left| \left(1 + \frac{k+1}{N}\right)^{-s} - \left(1 + \frac{k}{N}\right)^{-s} \right| = \left| f'(c) \frac{1}{N} \right|$$

And the error in that interval becomes bounded by $\left(M \frac{1}{N}\right) \frac{1}{N}$

Where M is the maximum absolute value of the first derivative of the function in that interval. And since we have N interval, then the total error is bounded by

$$|d_N(s)| \leq \frac{1}{N} \sup_{x \in [0,1]} |f'(x)|$$

In our case the function $f(x)$ is

$$f(x) = (1+x)^{-s}$$

$$f'(x) = -s(1+x)^{-s-1}$$

$$\sup_{x \in [0,1]} |f'(x)| = |s| 1^{-s-1} = |s|$$

Therefore,

$$|d_N(s)| \leq \frac{1}{N} |s|$$

$$|d_N(s)| \leq \frac{c}{N} \quad : c = |s|$$

$$\Rightarrow d_N(s) = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{N}\right)$$

$$(2N)^{1-s} d_N(s) = (2N)^{1-s} \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{N}\right) = \mathcal{O}(N^{1-s-1}) = \mathcal{O}(N^{-s})$$

And since $0 < \sigma < 1$ then $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} N^{-s} = 0$

And consequently $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} (2N)^{1-s} \left[\frac{1-2^{1-s}}{s-1} - \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \left(1 + \frac{k}{N}\right)^{-s} \right] = 0$